

THE MAIN DIFFERENCES OF SIMULTANEOUSLY AND CONSECUTIVE TRANSLATION

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“I just enjoy translating, it’s like opening one’s mouth and hearing someone else’s voice emerge.”

— Iris Murdoch

ABSTRACT: *For centuries, people from all over the world have engaged in translation and interpretation as a long-standing creative endeavor that is shaped by history and culture. It is the same across all of the earth's continents and areas. Since humans have existed for thousands of years, their progeny have used translation to express their creative interests, possibilities, and passions. It is an international communication tool that is consistently and successfully employed. Human nations are aware of one another thanks to translation and translators; this exchange took place. Due to their historical, social, and intellectual nature, linguistics attempts to establish equality and parity in its procedures. Translators and linguists are constantly at the forefront of their respective eras' cultures was operating Thus, among the domains that humanity has created, translation has emerged as an invaluable, valued, noble, and sophisticated endeavor.*

KEY WORDS: *translation, translator, oral, written, simultaneously, consecutive whispering.*

INTRODUCTION

When we are start to speak about translation, it is commonly known that it is not so easy process for everyone. As a half translator I can say that in the same time work can give two different opposite feeling during the activity. On the one hand translator deep in the situation and his job because of his interest. And it makes him

more emotional . On the other hand , translation is able to even make people like ‘ silence person ‘ from day to night. Owing to the fact that finding possible equivalence, trying to make differ a simple grammar from TL to SL, choosing right word combinations , these all of them can make alter the translator, sometimes even translator would lose all patience. Even though this skill is one of the admirable job from centuries. Translator was the main bridge between two countries during the diplomatic relations.

Regarding types of translation, there are 2 type of translation:

- **ORAL**
- **WRITTEN**

Our article will discuss concerning branches of oral translation and their differences . Oral translation is the way of speech which is translated orally by master of translations and linguistics. It includes :

- Simultaneous
- Consecutive
- Whispered

While all translation events share the fundamental qualities of translation, distinct forms of translation can be distinguished based on the source text's primary communication function or the speech form that is being translated procedure. As a result, we may differentiate between written and spoken translation (or interpretation), as well as between literary and informational translation.Literary pieces, such as poems or novels, are translated with the intention of evoking strong feelings or aesthetic responses in the reader. The main goal of the four translators is to convey the expressive nature of the source material accurately in translation, as this is what determines its communication worth.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Simultaneous and consecutive translation are two different methods used by

professional interpreters to facilitate communication between speakers of different languages. While both methods involve the transfer of information from one language to another, there are key differences between simultaneous and consecutive translation. Simultaneous translation, as the name suggests, refers to the process of interpreting and translating spoken words in real-time. Simultaneous interpreters listen to the speaker through headphones and quickly translate what is being said into the target language. This type of interpretation typically takes place in conferences, meetings, or large events where multiple language speakers are present. Simultaneous interpreters work in interpreting booths and rely on specialized equipment, including microphones, headsets, and an interpreting console, to interpret simultaneously for the audience. Due to the real-time nature of this method, simultaneous translation requires highly skilled interpreters who are able to think quickly, analyze information, and produce accurate translations on-the-spot.

Consecutive translation, on the other hand, involves the interpreter first listening to the speaker, taking notes, and then translating the speech into the target language after the speaker has finished. The interpreter typically stands or sits next to the speaker and takes notes during the speech or presentation. Once the speaker has finished a segment, the interpreter translates that segment into the target language aloud. This method is less immediate than simultaneous translation, as there is a time lag between the speaker's words and the interpreter's translation. Consecutive translation is often used in smaller settings such as business meetings, negotiations, interviews, or court proceedings, where immediate communication is not always necessary. One of the main differences between simultaneous and consecutive translation is the timing and delivery of the translation. Simultaneous interpreters need to have excellent linguistic and cognitive abilities, as they must listen, analyze, and translate simultaneously without interrupting the flow of the speaker. As a result, simultaneous interpretation requires more intense

concentration and can be mentally and physically demanding. On the other hand, consecutive interpreters have the advantage of time to process and prepare their translations, allowing them to deliver a more accurate and polished interpretation.

Another key difference is the equipment used in each type of interpretation. Simultaneous interpretation requires interpreting booths, soundproof headsets, microphones, and an interpreting console, which can be expensive and require technical support. Consecutive interpretation, while it may require some basic equipment such as a note pad or recording device, is generally more flexible and can be conducted without the need for specialized equipment. Furthermore, simultaneous interpretation is considered more efficient for large events with many participants, as it allows for a seamless flow of communication without disrupting the overall event. In contrast, consecutive interpretation can be more time-consuming, as it requires the speaker to pause after each segment, leading to longer meeting or event durations. In summary, simultaneous and consecutive translation have distinct differences in terms of timing, delivery, equipment requirements, and overall efficiency. The choice between the two methods depends on factors such as the nature of the event, the number of participants, the desired level of immediacy, and the resources available.

When *simultaneous interpreting* is used, the interpreter listens to the speaker using a headset while seated in an interpreting booth and provides commentary into a microphone. Through a headset, conference room attendees hear the version in the target language. Sign language interpreters, often known as deaf interpreters, also provide simultaneous interpretations from spoken to signed language and the other way around. Interpreters that speak sign languages stand in the conference room, where they can see the speaker and be seen by other attendees, rather than sitting in a booth. Whispered interpreting is a type of simultaneous interpreting where the interpreter sits next to the delegate who requires the interpreting rather than in a booth in the conference room, whispering the speech in the delegate's ears

in the target language.

These interpretation techniques are not limited to conference settings. For example, whispered interpreting may be utilized in a business meeting, whereas simultaneous interpreting has been employed at huge conferences and forums. These days, special equipment is used for simultaneous translation. Delegates listen to what is being said in the booth directly into the microphone of the interpreters who are listening. The interpreters wear headphones that allow them to translate through a microphone to the delegates who are wearing them. Even in the absence of gadgets, some simultaneous translation can be performed by whispering. One of the participants speaks, and another needs an interpreter's simultaneous translation assistance; at most, he whispers the translation into the ears of two individuals. Some psychologists and linguists studying simultaneous translation in the 1960s and early 1970s developed an interest in a number of experiential translation courses and fundamental various language techniques, the rate at which messages are received, the intervals between messages, the duration of language conversion, and concerns like speech pauses during arrival have all been researched. Currently, there is a lack of scientific research on the ideas and methods of simultaneous translation from Uzbek to English and from English to Uzbek. As may be shown, consecutive and simultaneous translation are employed at conferences and other events. Interpreter: The speaker's words are important to him, not his actions. For interrogators and interpreters, specialized equipment is available.

Oral communication between speakers of various languages might be translated simultaneously or consecutively. The topic of consecutive interpreter training is one that is discussed a lot. One explanation is that there is a progressive disappearance of consecutive translation. The majority of scientists in Western Europe make this claim, although scientists in Asia and Eastern Europe disagree. After the speaker in the source language has completed a section of his speech, the interpreter continues speaking in sequential interpreting. The speaker in the source

language is given the opportunity to talk in segments, while the interpreter either stands or sits next to them, listening and taking notes. The interpreter converts the message into the target language when the speaker pauses or ends their speech and it is the main difference from simultaneous translation. In addition this type of translation is more popular around the world. Because the given pauses seem easier than first one.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, a translator is a master of the art of revealing the subtleties of this language. Being a simultaneous interpreter requires years of experience, more time and work. Moreover, precisely because of these features, this method of translation is expensive. Through the method of consecutive translation, the translator can improve his simultaneous translation skills.

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